

Reduction-Based MAX-3SAT with Low Nonlinearity and Lattices Under Recombination

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Abstract. A new construction is introduced for creating random MAX-3SAT instances with low nonlinearity. Instead of generating random clauses, we generate random SAT expressions over 3 variables and then convert these into CNF SAT clauses. We prove that this yields structured problems with much lower nonlinearity. We also introduce a new method for weighting MAX-SAT clauses that preserves low nonlinearity and also breaks up plateaus. We evaluate these new problems by enumeration of instances with $n = 30$ variables. One unexpected result is that Partition Crossover creates more tunnels on these semi-structured MAX-SAT problems compared to results on random NK landscapes. We show that Partition Crossover induces hypercube lattices over subsets of local optima; all of the local optima which appear in a lattice can be evaluated with a single linear equation.

Keywords: MAX-SAT · Recombination Operators · Partition Crossover · Evolutionary Combinatorial Optimization.

1 Introduction

MAX-SAT optimization has a long history in the combinatorial optimization and AI communities. MAX-SAT solvers have applications in hardware and software verification, as well as in related problems of model checking, constraint satisfaction, subset selection, scheduling and planning problems [8,20].

In general, there are two broad classes of MAX-SAT solvers: exact methods and inexact heuristic methods. Modern exact solvers display excellent results in many real-world applications. Inexact solvers are typically based on stochastic local search algorithms and have their roots in earlier methods such as GSAT [25] and WalkSAT [26]; they display excellent results on random instances [3,24].

Typically, industrial satisfiability applications display lower nonlinearity compared to randomly generated MAX-SAT instances. This nonlinearity can be measured by taking the Fourier transform of the problem instance and counting the number of nonlinear coefficients that appear in the resulting polynomial.

This paper has two goals. First, deterministic forms of recombination have been developed in the field of evolutionary computation. What can we transfer from work on the Traveling Salesman Problem and on k -bounded pseudo-Boolean functions to the MAX-SAT domain? We also discuss new opportunities for improving evolutionary algorithms for MAX-SAT.

Second, how can we generate random MAX-SAT problems that are more like real-world problems? This second goal is also motivated by renewed interest in transforms that can convert highly nonlinear Boolean functions into a quadratic form [5,7,6]. These transforms are of interest to the Adiabatic Quantum Computing research community [12] since this community typically converts their optimization problems into Quadratic Unconstrained Boolean Optimization problems (QUBO). This idea should be familiar to computer scientists, since “transforms” are closely related to the “reductions” that are used to prove NP-completeness by mapping one problem class onto another problem class [11]. A keystone reduction in NP-completeness theory is the reduction that maps all satisfiability problems (SAT) onto the class of MAX-3SAT problems. Ansoategui et al. [2] have proposed new random SAT generators based on the power-law distribution, which is followed by industrial SAT instances [1]. We propose here an alternative way of generating random industrial-like MAX-SAT instances.

We stress that transforms and reductions can *smash* nonlinearity. Reductions and transforms can take problem instances with exponential nonlinearity as input and output a problem instance with dramatically bounded nonlinearity. Given any pseudo-Boolean function, transforms can output a quadratic form for QUBO instances or a cubic form for MAX-3SAT instances. This is a powerful idea, but it has not been used often in the evolutionary computation community, despite Kaufman’s theoretical work suggesting that DNA may be characterized by k -bounded interactions [21].

Section 2 introduce a novel way to generate random MAX-3SAT instances with low nonlinearity, creating problems that are closer to real-world applications. This new method also builds on the idea that most real-world applications are constructed using either transforms or higher-order logical expressions and logical constraints. In section 3 we introduce a new way to “weight” MAX-SAT instances that preserves lower nonlinearity. Surprisingly, these MAX-3SAT problems with randomized weights superficially resemble random NK landscapes.

In section 4 we discuss Partition Crossover and its properties. Partition crossover induces lattices of local optima and sub-local optima. A **sub-local optima** is a solution that is locally optima in a hypercube subspace of the full search space. While one could define numerous hyperplane subspaces, we limit our attention to hyperplane subspaces that are induced by recombination events where the parents are themselves local optima in the full search space.

In section 5 we enumerate all of the local optima for small weighted MAX-3SAT instances. We also enumerate all lattices that can be obtained by recombining all possible pairs of local optima. We find that these weighted MAX-3SAT instances induce more lattices than similar NK landscapes and thus appear to be more “searchable” than NK landscapes using Partition Crossover.

2 A New Construction for MAX-3SAT Problems

It is commonly assumed that real-world MAX-SAT applications have significantly lower degrees of nonlinearity than randomly generated MAX-SAT benchmarks [20,8]. It is often suggested that this is true because real-world problems have regular structure and repeating logical constraints. However, it is common to use “reductions” to convert a general satisfiability problem (SAT) to MAX-SAT. These reductions are a type of transform that reduces nonlinearity by adding additional auxiliary variables [6,7,11].

Thus, do industrial applications have low nonlinearity because of their regular structure, or because transforms have been used to convert these problems in MAX-SAT instances? We will show that the use of transforms can also generate random MAX-3SAT instances with surprisingly low nonlinearity.

The classic textbook on “Algorithms” by Cormen et al. [11] reduces the following 3 variable expression to Conjunctive Normal Form (CNF):

$$(y1 \iff (y2 \wedge \neg x2))$$

This expression is exactly as it appears in Cormen’s reduction example. Variable $x2$ is a variable in the original SAT expression. Variables $y1$ and $y2$ are auxiliary variables used to convert the SAT expression into a binary tree. This 3 variable expression is then converted into the following four CNF clauses:

$$(\neg y1 \vee \neg y2 \vee \neg x2) \wedge (\neg y1 \vee y2 \vee \neg x2) \wedge (\neg y1 \vee y2 \vee x2) \wedge (y1 \vee \neg y2 \vee x2)$$

Note that each clause is made false by exactly one (distinct) assignment so that only one clause at a time is false. **This generalizes to all possible sets of 4 distinct CNF clauses over the same 3 variables.** The four assignments which make exactly one of the above CNF clauses false in our example are (in order): 111, 101, 100, 010. Because they share the same variables, these clauses combine into one subfunction (mapping the bit strings to integers), which we write in a single line as follows:

$$f_i(y1, y2, x2) = \overbrace{4}^{000}, \overbrace{4}^{001}, \overbrace{3}^{010}, \overbrace{4}^{011}, \overbrace{3}^{100}, \overbrace{3}^{101}, \overbrace{4}^{110}, \overbrace{3}^{111}$$

This can be shifted by a constant to yield

$$f_i(y1, y2, x2) = 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0$$

This is now a standard truth table over the 3 variables and gives us a unique way to identify all possible such constructions. In general, there are $\binom{2^k}{c}$ logical expressions over k variables assuming there are c clauses, and for every CNF clause there is 1 way in which is it false.

For MAX-3SAT, $k = 3$ and $c = 4$ when there are 4 clauses. Thus we have exactly $\binom{8}{4} = 70$ logical expressions. We next compute the Walsh transform of these functions (which is identical to the Hadamard or discrete square-wave

Fourier Transform). Given a Boolean function $f : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, the i^{th} Walsh coefficient for f is defined as:

$$w_i^{(f)} = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} f(x)(-1)^{x \cdot i}, \quad (1)$$

where $x \cdot i$ denotes the dot product of the binary string x and the binary string represented by integer i .

Lemma 1. *Let $f : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a Boolean function with c unsatisfiable input combinations (zeroes). Let \bar{f} represent its complement. Then the Walsh coefficients of f and \bar{f} are related as follows:*

$$w_i^{(\bar{f})} = -w_i^{(f)} \quad \forall i \neq 0, \quad (2)$$

$$w_0^{(\bar{f})} = 1 - w_0^{(f)} = \frac{c}{2^n}. \quad (3)$$

Proof. Using Eq. (1) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} w_i^{(\bar{f})} &= \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} (1 - f(x))(-1)^{x \cdot i} \\ &= \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} (-1)^{x \cdot i} - \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} f(x)(-1)^{x \cdot i} \\ &= \delta_i^0 - w_i^{(f)} \end{aligned}$$

where we used the fact that $\sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} (-1)^{x \cdot i} = 2^n \delta_i^0$ (see [27]). We complete the proof with the following expression:

$$w_0^{(\bar{f})} = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} (1 - f(x))(-1)^0 = \frac{c}{2^n}$$

□

According to Lemma 1, if we have a function with $n = 3$ and $c = 4$ unsatisfying assignments, $w_0^{(\bar{f})} = 1 - w_0^{(f)} = 4/8 = 0.5$.

This lemma tells us that to evaluate the nonlinearity of functions with $k = 3$ and $c = 4$ we only need to consider 35 cases. The following is a sample of 7 of the 35 cases, as well as the complement of the penultimate string (as an example). The coefficients and polynomials were generated using a Walsh transform.

	w_0	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1	0.5	0	0	0	-0.5	0	0	0
0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1	0.5	-0.25	-0.25	0	-0.25	0	0	0.25
0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1	0.5	0	-0.25	-0.25	-0.25	0.25	0	0
0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1	0.5	-0.25	0	-0.25	-0.25	0	0.25	0
0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1	0.5	0	0	0	-0.25	-0.25	0.25	-0.25
0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1	0.5	-0.25	0.25	0	-0.25	0	0	-0.25
0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0	0.5	0	0.25	-0.25	-0.25	-0.25	0	0
1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1	0.5	0	-0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0	0

Note that w_0 is a constant, the coefficients w_3, w_5, w_6 are quadratic and w_7 is cubic. The other coefficients are linear. It is easy to prove that for every coefficient w_i with $i \neq 0$, 36 of the 70 entries are zero⁴. This also removes more than half of the cubic coefficients, w_7 .

What is striking about this simple result is the fact that these random MAX-3SAT constructions display very low nonlinearity.

By contrast, here are the Walsh coefficients for a single example clause.

	w_0	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1	0.875	0.125	0.125	-0.125	-0.125	0.125	0.125	-0.125

By enumeration, every possible single clause has coefficients with weights $w_0 = 7/8 = 0.875$ and $w_i = \pm 1/8 = \pm 0.125$. (The signs are the negation of one column of the corresponding 8 by 8 Walsh matrix.)

Next, assume we generate a random MAX-3SAT instance by generating a random 3-variable SAT expression and then we convert it into 4 CNF clauses. We will refer to these as Reduction-based MAX-3SAT instances, or *Reduced MAX-3SAT* to be more concise. Assume this instance also has m clauses. In expectation, the majority of cubic terms in a Reduced MAX-3SAT instance will cancel. First, for every 4 CNF clauses that touch the same 3 variables, there is only one possible cubic term. Second, with a probability of 36/70 the possible cubic term of the corresponding Walsh polynomial over the 4 CNF clauses will be zero. If $m = 4n$ the number of cubic terms is approximately $n/2$ instead of the $4n$ we would expect for m completely random clauses. *This represents an 8 fold decrease in cubic terms.* In addition, the Reduced MAX-3SAT instance will have approximately $3n$ quadratic coefficients compared to the approximately $12n$ quadratic terms we would expect for m completely random clauses. And, again with probability 36/70 each possible quadratic term of the corresponding Walsh polynomial over the 4 CNF clauses will be zero. Thus, by generating random SAT expressions (truth tables) over 3 variables, and then converting these into MAX-3SAT expressions, the level of nonlinearity is dramatically reduced.

We will express these arguments in terms of the expected number of Walsh Coefficients Per Clause (WPC). Let v denote the clause-to-variable ratio of a MAX-SAT instance so that $m = vn$

Theorem 1. *Assume that all variable interactions are unique for each clause or for each Reduced MAX-3SAT subfunction and all linear coefficients are non-zero. Assume $m = vn$. Then the Walsh Coefficients Per Clause (WPC) for Reduced MAX-3SAT instances is $WPC < 1/v + 0.5$. The Walsh Coefficients Per Clause (WPC) for standard random MAX-3SAT instances is $WPC = 4 + 1/v$.*

Proof. There are n linear coefficients. If $m = vn$ the WPC for linear coefficients is $n/m = 1/v$. We next use counting arguments from lemma 1. For Reduced MAX-SAT, there are only 3 quadratic coefficients for every 4 CNF clauses. More than

⁴ In general, each Walsh coefficient except w_0 is zero in $\binom{2^k-1}{c/2}^2$ out of $\binom{2^k}{c}$ functions.

half of these are zero (36/70 to be precise) in expectation. Thus, the number of quadratic terms is bounded by $(3/4m * 0.5)$ and $WPC < 3/8$ for the quadratic coefficients. Finally, the number of cubic terms is bounded by $m/4 * 0.5$ and $WPC < 1/8$. Since we assume that all variable interactions per clause are unique, a normal random MAX-3SAT clause has 3 quadratic and 1 cubic terms per clause, all with weight ± 0.125 and $WPC = 1/v + 4$. \square

Of course, all variable interactions are not unique, but if $m = O(n)$, the variable interactions of random instances have a high probability of being unique. For quadratic interactions, we are sampling $O(n)$ elements from $O(n^2)$ choices, and for cubic interactions, we are sampling $O(n)$ elements from $O(n^3)$ choices.

If $m = 4n$ (which is close to the random MAX-3SAT phase transition [22]) standard random MAX-3SAT instance will have an expected approximate WPC = 4.25. However, for a Reduced MAX-3SAT instance the expected approximate WPC = 0.75. There is a dramatic difference in nonlinearity.

The Reduced MAX-3SAT instances are compared with 14 large industrial problems from the MAX-SAT 2012 challenge⁵ to determine their level of non-linearity. Problem size ranged from 247,943 to 2,766,036 variables. These real-world problems have a median WPC of just 1.17 Walsh coefficients per clause (for the mem-control problem) [17]. Table 1 shows that the WPC ranges from 1.69 (the maximum) to 0.73 (the minimum). $WPC = 1.26$ is the second largest and $WPC = 0.978$ is the second smallest.

Table 1: WPC of five instances of the MAX-SAT 2012 competition.

Problem Name	b15	fpu	mem control	wb-46	rsd-KES
WPC	1.69	1.26	1.17	0.978	0.73

For these industrial problems, the WPC is between 0.978 and 1.26 for 12 of the 14 industrial problems. As can be seen, our Reduced MAX-3SAT problems have slightly lower WPC than these industrial problems. But the WPC of our Reduced MAX-3SAT problems is much closer to these industrial problems than the WPC of standard random MAX-3SAT instances, where the typical WPC is greater than 4.1 for problems near the phase transition.

Our Reduced MAX-3SAT problems could be preprocessed to remove some variables and clauses. Some output vectors (truth tables) have lower nonlinearity because they express simple constraints on the MAX-3SAT constructions.

For example, if the variables are x_1, x_2, x_3 then the following linear constraints represents the truth table where $x_3 = 1$ (x_3 is true).

	w_0	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1	0.5	0	0	0	-0.5	0	0	0

⁵ <http://MAX-SAT.ia.udl.cat/>

Thus, the resulting Walsh polynomial only has one linear coefficient. Variable x_3 could be removed, as well as the associated clauses that are satisfied by x_3 by standard unit propagation (which would increase the WPC). This would also reduce the size of clauses that reference x_3 . This kind of preprocessing is normal for real-world applications [14].

3 Weighted MAX-3SAT

Weighting MAX-SAT instances has various purposes. Weights may be used to distinguish between hard constraints that are important (for clauses that must be satisfied) and soft constraints (clauses one would prefer to satisfy, but satisfaction is not a hard constraint) [23].

For MAX-kSAT instances, local optima may not be well-defined because of very large plateaus in the search space [15,19]. We use weighted MAX-SAT instances to break ties when possible, and thus break up the potentially large plateaus that commonly occur in the landscape of MAX-kSAT instances.

We have as an additional goal to minimize nonlinearity to the degree possible. We introduce a new way to add weights so that the weights do not increase the number of 3-way cubic interactions in the Walsh polynomial.

First, consider the following 4 MAX-SAT clauses over the same 3 variables and its Walsh transform.

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{array}{cccccccc} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ \hline \text{Walsh} & w_0 & w_1 & w_2 & w_3 & w_4 & w_5 & w_6 & w_7 \\ 0.5 & 0 & -0.25 & 0.25 & 0.25 & 0.25 & 0 & 0 \end{array}$$

Next, the UNSAT assignments are given a very small distinct weight, while the SAT assignments are all weighted by 4, so that the global maximum returns the total of clauses satisfied. Next, we again compute the Walsh coefficients.

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{array}{cccccccc} 4 & 0.12 & 4 & 4 & 0.13 & 0.11 & 0.14 & 4 \\ \hline \text{Walsh} & w_0 & w_1 & w_2 & w_3 & w_4 & w_5 & w_6 & w_7 \\ 2.0625 & 0.005 & -0.9725 & 0.97 & 0.9675 & 0.965 & 0.0025 & 0.0 \end{array}$$

Note that the cubic term is still zero: $w_7 = w_{111} = 0.0$. This is because the Walsh signs cause the weight to cancel: $w_7 = 0.14 + 0.11 - 0.12 - 0.13 = 0$.

The weights can be scaled to be arbitrarily small, while also ensuring that any ranking ordering of solutions can be preserved.

$$w_7 = w_{111} = 0.00014 + 0.00011 - 0.00012 - 0.00013 = 0.0.$$

Fortunately, even very small weights are sufficient to disrupt plateaus and allow smaller distinct local optima (or smaller plateaus) to form. Note that these weights can be quasi-random except they must sum to zero. In practice, three weights can be random, and the fourth weight is then determined.

Fig. 1: Variable interaction graph (VIG) for example F1 as well as the decomposed recombination graph for P1 and P2.

4 Partition Crossover, Local Optima and Lattices

Partition crossover is a deterministic recombination operator that breaks the parents into linear separable recombining components [28]. In general, this is only possible if the evaluation function has limited nonlinearity. But many NP-hard problems do display limited nonlinearity, including MAX-kSAT [9,10], NK landscapes, QUBO, and the Traveling Salesman Problem [18].

We will use a MAX-3SAT example borrowed from Dunton [13]. The following function F1 has $m = 18$ subfunctions and $n = 24$ variables. The subfunction are labeled from f_a to f_z (but using only 18 characters). The variables are labeled with integers from 1 to 24, where integer i denotes variable x_i .

$$\begin{array}{lllll}
 \text{F1: } f_a: 1\ 2\ 3 & f_b: 2\ 3\ 4 & f_c: 3\ 4\ 5 & f_d: 4\ 5\ 6 & f_e: 5\ 6\ 7 \\
 f_r: 6\ 7\ 23 & f_h: 8\ 9\ 22 & f_i: 8\ 10\ 23 & f_j: 11\ 12\ 13 & f_s: 8\ 9\ 10 \\
 f_k: 11\ 13\ 22 & f_l: 11\ 20\ 21 & f_m: 11\ 21\ 22 & f_n: 14\ 15\ 24 & \\
 f_o: 14\ 16\ 17 & f_p: 15\ 16\ 17 & f_q: 16\ 17\ 20 & f_z: 18\ 19\ 21 &
 \end{array}$$

Figure 1 shows the variable interaction graph (VIG) for function F1. A VIG is a graph where vertices represent variables, and there is an edge $e(v_i, v_j)$ if and only if there is a nonlinear interaction between vertex v_i and v_j .

Figure 1 is based on a specific MAX-3SAT instance and we will assume that none of the Walsh coefficients are zero. In practice, it is important to use Walsh coefficients when computing the VIG for Reduced MAX-3SAT functions. Removing the canceled interactions can reduce the number of edges in the VIG by 50%. When $m = O(n)$ the resulting VIG has $O(n)$ edges, and the total number of coefficients in the resulting Walsh polynomial is $O(n)$. Thus, the VIG is computed in $O(n)$ time using the Walsh transform. The VIG is only computed once.

Let P1 denote Parent 1 and P2 denote Parent 2. Furthermore, assume P1 and P2 are local optima under a Hamming bit-flip neighborhood⁶. The first step of Partition Crossover for k-bounded pseudo-Boolean function is to remove

⁶ However, any neighborhood local search operator will suffice.

vertices from the VIG that corresponds to variables where P1 and P2 have a shared assignment (both 1 or both 0). Thus, the variables that remain in the VIG are always complements (0 and 1, or 1 and 0). After variables with the same assignment are removed, the VIG is often decomposed into q connected subgraphs. Let the two parent solutions P1 and P2 be:

$$\begin{aligned} P1 &= 01000\ 01100\ 10000\ 01101\ 1111 \\ P2 &= 10111\ 10011\ 01111\ 10011\ 1111 \end{aligned}$$

These two solutions share only the last 5 bits in common. After vertices 20 to 24 (x_{20} to x_{24}) are deleted, there are five connected subgraphs. Figure 1b shows the shattered graph for function F1, and parents P1 and P2. This “shattered graph” represents the “recombination graph.”

Assuming that the VIG is shattered into q connected subgraphs, the evaluation function $f(x)$ can (temporarily) be decomposed into a set of new subfunctions $g_1(x) \cdots g_q(x)$. Let x' denote any string where the shared bits in P1 and P2 are fixed. Then

$$f(x') = g(x') = \sum_{i=1}^q g_i(x')$$

The new subfunctions $g_i(x')$ decomposes both the set of subfunctions as well as the set of variables. Logically it follows that if the VIG has been shattered, this must decompose both the variables and the subfunctions. For example, in the shattered recombination graph in Figure 1, variables 14, 15, 16, 17 are associated with the original subfunctions f_n, f_o, f_p, f_q while variables 11, 12, 13 are associated with the original subfunctions f_j, f_k, f_l, f_m .

4.1 Lattices and Linear Equations

There exists a simple linear equation that can be used to evaluate all of the children of parents P1 and P2 under Partition Crossover. This can be applied to all k -bounded pseudo-Boolean functions, as well as Traveling Salesman Problems when using Partition Crossover.

Let q denote the number of recombining components. Let b denote an auxiliary binary string of length q . Let $b_i = 0$ denote that the offspring inherits bits from parent 2 in the i^{th} recombining component. Similarly, $b_i = 1$ denotes that the offspring inherits bits from parent 1 in the i^{th} recombining component. When $b = 1^q$ all bits are inherited from P1 (the offspring is a copy of P1). When $b = 0^q$ all bits are inherited from P2 (the offspring is a copy of P2).

Theorem 2 (Theorem 3.1 in [29]). *Under Partition Crossover, all of the 2^q children of parents P1 and P2 can be evaluated using the following linear equation and the auxiliary bit function b . For any child x_c*

$$f(x_c) = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i b_i \tag{4}$$

where $\alpha_0 = f(P2)$ and $f(P1) = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i$.

Fig. 2: The big-valley (fitness-distance correlation) plot shows the relative location of local optima where Hamming distance from the global optimum is plotted on the x -axis, and fitness is on the y -axis. But looking closely, the big-valley plot is also a 4D Hamming cube associated with 16 local optima generated by one Partition Crossover event. The big-valley distribution is plotted in terms of minimization instead of maximization.

Assume the objective function is a random NK landscape, and we discover a lattice with $q = 7$ recombining components, and the linear equation which is induced is given by

$$f(x) = \alpha_0 + 7b_1 - 143b_2 - 29b_3 + 52b_4 + 83b_5 - 16b_6 + 66b_7.$$

The bit mask returns the best possible offspring out of 128 possible children by selecting only the positive coefficients (assuming maximization). Thus the b vector for the best possible offspring is $b = 1001101$.

Note that the b vector defines a hypercube which in some sense *organizes* the offspring. This hypercube induces a non-planar *lattice*.

A **lattice** is a partially ordered set containing the children and parents of a Partition Crossover event. In some sense, a lattice is just a weighted Hamming cube. A lattice can be ordered by both fitness, as well as Hamming distance. All of these children and parents in a lattice are related in fitness via Equation (4). Tinos et al. [28] proved that if the parents are local optima, then all children of Partition Crossover must also be locally optima in the smallest hyperplane subspace that contains the parents. If all of the children are local optima in the search space, then all of these local optima have a fitness value determined by Equation (4). **Thus, the evaluations of local optima in the search are not arbitrary, but rather determined by the lattices to which they belong as well as by Equation (4).** This is true for all local optima that appear in at least one Partition Crossover lattice.

A 4D Hamming cube is shown in Figure 2, as well as the big-valley (fitness-distance correlation) plot of local optima generated by single specific Partition Crossover event. A big-valley plot is a plot of local optima with fitness on the y -axis and Hamming distance (usually relative to the global optimum) on the x -axis. A big-valley plot is traditionally shown in terms of **minimization** as

is the case here. Because Hamming distance is itself a linear calculation, there is also a linear equation function for Hamming distance with respect to the b vector used in Equation 4. All of the 16 children shown in Figure 2b are local optima. Careful inspection of Figure 2b shows that these local optima also form a 4D hypercube, weighted by $2b_1 + 2b_2 + 4b_3 + 5b_4$ for Hamming distance relative to the best child, and $85b_1 + 59b_2 + 64b_3 + 75b_4$ for fitness (with respect to 0,0 for the best solution). Only complementary strings can regenerate the entire lattice. Complementary bit strings can be either far apart or close together in terms of fitness. All complementary offspring are equidistant from the evaluation $(f(P1) + f(P2))/2$ and any relative Hamming distance $(HD(P1) + HD(P2))/2$. This is not a coincidence, and it impacts the probability that Partition Crossover is able to find improving moves. This also illustrates why it is important to see the Hamming cube containing all of the children as a lattice. The lattice organizes the children in terms of both fitness and relative Hamming distance.

5 Enumeration Results

In this section, we look at the hypercube lattices associated with both NK landscapes, as well as Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT instances. We do this by enumerating all of the local optima in the search space for problems with $n = 30$ variables. After we enumerate all of the local optima in the search space, we then recombine all pairs of local optima in the search space. This yields all lattices that can be reached by recombining local optima. In the case of Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT instances, local optima sometimes take the form of relatively small plateaus of solutions with equal fitness.

5.1 A Trick to Enumerate Local Optima

The enumeration of local optima often **does not** require enumeration of the entire search space. If we have the Walsh coefficients for a k -bounded pseudo-Boolean function, we also know which variables have nonlinear interactions.

Assume $n = 30$ bits (n can be arbitrary), and that we know that when starting from the string 0^{30} that an improving move can be obtained by flipping bit number 25. Thus 0^{30} is not a local optimum. Furthermore assume that we know that bit 25 interacts only with bits 23, 25, 29, 30. Until some bit is changed that has a nonlinear interaction with bit 25, any string (solution) that we visit cannot be a local optimum (because flipping bit 25 still produces an improving move). Thus we can identify hyperplanes of the search that can be ignored (and thus eliminated) because they do not contain a local optimum. In this way, all local optima can be found without enumerating the entire search space [16].

5.2 Empirical Results and Trends

Table 1 presents empirical data based on enumeration. We enumerated the local optima in 10 random NK landscapes and 10 Reduced MAX-3SAT instances.

There are $n=30$ variables for all problems. By enumerating these smaller problems, we can answer questions that would be impossible otherwise.

The random NK landscapes and the Reduced MAX-3SAT instances used exactly the same random variable interaction graphs. Thus exactly the same random assignment of variables to subfunctions was used for both classes of problems. Any differences are **not** due to the variable interaction graph. All 8 values in the subfunctions of the NK landscape are random; for the Reduced MAX-3SAT instances 4 out of 8 values are a constant (when all 4 clauses are satisfied) while 4 values correspond to a different randomized penalty when one clause is not satisfied. Thus, differences should be due to the reduction in the nonlinearity in our construction of Reduced MAX-3SAT instances.

We note that only one of the 10 MAX-3SAT instances is satisfiable, and 9 instances are UNSAT. For 3 of the other 9 instances 119 out of 120 clauses were satisfiable. Next, 118 out of 120 clauses were satisfiable for 3 of 9 instances, and 117 out of 120 clauses were satisfiable for 3 instances. Keep in mind these are true global optima. This also likely means that **the phase transition for Reduced MAX-3SAT is different than that of standard random MAX-3SAT instances.**

All of our problems have a variable-to-clause ratio of 4.0. The phase transition for standard random MAX-3SAT instances is a 4.27 variable to clause ratio [22]. Thus, we had expected that more than one of our Reduced MAX-3SAT instances would also be satisfiable. We conjecture that Reduced MAX-3SAT has a phase transition that is less than 4.0, as it also the case with other real-like random instances [4]. Note that an instance with a global optimum of 119 out of 120 clauses could be made SAT by deleting just one clause.

For the random NK landscapes, we present average results for various metrics. For the Reduced MAX-3SAT instances we show a range of problem instances ranked by number of local optima (which corresponds exactly to the ranking by number of lattices). We show the averages for the various metrics, as well as the specific metrics for the problems with rank 1, 4, 7 and 10.

The metrics include, among others, the number of local optima and the number of global solutions. For MAX-3SAT in particular there can be numerous ties for the global optimum, and the global optima was always part of a plateau. There were more globally optimal solutions when the evaluation of the global optima was 117 or 118. Thus, when the problems were more constrained (and the global optimum satisfied fewer clauses) there were larger plateaus and multiple plateaus representing multiple global optima that were easier to find. This also provides additional evidence that the phase transition for Reduced MAX-3SAT is likely different than that of standard random MAX-3SAT instances.

One thing that is notable is that Reduced MAX-3SAT instances have far more local optima than NK landscape where $k=3$ ($K=2$). These local optima also induce more tunnels between optima, and more pathways to the global optima. The number of lattices that reach a globally optimal solution is surprisingly high, but there is great variance between samples.

Table 2: Empirical data collected by enumerating all local optima for $N=30$. All numbers are averages of 10 instances, except there were 9 MAX-3SAT instances. The Random NK landscapes results are averages. The symbol # denotes a count in this table.

	NK		Reduced MAX-3SAT Instances			
	Random	MAX-3SAT	Rank 1	Rank 4	Rank 7	Rank 10
	Mean	Mean	Seed 1	Seed 9	Seed 6	Seed 4
Local Optima #	485	1984	659	1597	2434	3095
Size 4 lattices	27,348	912,362	54,131	435,155	1,002,621	3,216,771
Size 8 lattices	4,280	492,550	11,144	182,632	390,446	2,538,847
Size 16 lattices	284	192,817	771	58,730	107,157	1,227,573
Size 32 lattices	1	53,119	7	14,767	17,820	392,258
Size 64 lattices	0	9,056	0	2,197	1,282	75,693
Size 128 lattices	0	768	0	98	16	6,940
Size 256 lattices	0	21	0	0	0	208
Size 512 lattices	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Lattices	31,915	1,662,694	66,053	693,579	1,539,342	7,458,290
Crossover Success	21%	51%	30.46%	54.42%	51.98%	75.78%
Sub-Opt Children	26%	11.6%	8.58%	12.83%	12.62%	15.91%
Global Solutions	1.2	12.6	4	108	54	444
Clauses Satisfied	na	118.2	119	118	120	117
Global Lattices%	1.79%	9.4%	1.55%	13.55%	20.32%	20.61%

An additional metric is the crossover success frequency: when PX is used to recombine two local optima, how often does that recombination produce offspring? The crossover success frequency is lower for random NK landscapes: 21 percent of the time PX produces offspring. For Reduced MAX-3SAT problems the crossover success frequency is 51 percent.

We also report the total number of lattices found as well as how many lattices were found of specific size (from size 4 to 512, corresponding to $q=2$ to $q=9$ recombining components). On average there were 1,662,694 lattices found for Reduced MAX-3SAT instances. There were on average only 31,915 lattices found for random NK landscapes. The number of lattices found is related to both the Crossover Success rate and the number of local optima. As the number of lattices increases, the size of the largest lattices also increases. The Reduced MAX-3SAT instances sometimes included lattices of sizes 128, 256 and 512. There were no lattices of size larger than 32 for random NK landscapes.

We also report the number of sub-optima (children of PX that were not locally optimal). This was highest for random NK landscapes at 26 percent, so that 74 percent of all children were also local optima in the full space. For Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT 88 percent of all children were also local optima. Of course, the local optima of Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT problems are often small plateaus.

And finally, what percentage of the lattices included a globally optimal solution? For Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT this was 9.4% percent. This sounds very encouraging, but this number should be taken with a grain of salt. Not every lattice that contains a globally optimal solution is equally easy to discover, and for some lattices of size 4, reaching the global optimum could be difficult. Furthermore, if we only look at the MAX-3SAT with 119/120 clauses satisfied, the percentage is only 3.14%. For these instances, the global plateaus were much smaller and hard to find. On the other hand, for the single SAT instance (120/120 clauses satisfied), the percentage is 20.32%. A better understanding of the phase transition for Reduced MAX-3SAT problems should shed additional light on the question of problem difficulty.

Overall, this empirical data suggests that Reduced MAX-3SAT instances can often be searched effectively using Partition Crossover as an operator. Reduced MAX-3SAT instances also seem much easier to search than random NK landscapes. More work is needed to understand whether problems drawn from closer to a phase transition might be more difficult than the problems we have sampled.

6 Conclusions

This paper explores the nonlinearity of MAX-SAT instances, and introduces weighted and unweighted Reduced MAX-3SAT problems which display low nonlinearity; low linearity is more typically associated with industrial MAX-SAT applications. Standard randomly generated MAX-3SAT instances have a Walsh coefficient per clause count that is approximately 5 times larger than unweighted Reduced MAX-3SAT ($4.25/0.75 > 5$); all of these additional coefficients are quadratic and cubic variable interactions. A new way to create Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT problems is also described which does not introduce any additional cubic variable interactions.

Finally, we look at how Partition Crossover can be applied to Weighted Reduced MAX-3SAT problems. Partition crossover induces hypercube lattices over subsets of local optima which are found when Partition Crossover is used to recombine two locally optimal solutions. In this paper, the local optima are induced by a single-bit flip neighborhood. By enumerating local optima for instances with $n = 30$ variables, we found that Partition Crossover is highly successful at “tunneling” between local optima. More work is needed to understand the phase transition of Reduced MAX-3SAT problems and how this might impact problem difficulty.

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